

Tl(III) Oxidation of Alpha-Hydroxy Acids

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The reactions of some alpha-hydroxy acids with Tl(III) acetate in aqueous acetic acid have been studied. All the reactions have been found to obey second order kinetics. $Tl(OAc)_3^+$ has been shown to be the active oxidant in aqueous acetic acid media. The kinetic constants have been evaluated and discussed.

THERE are a number of reports on the kinetics of oxidation of alpha-hydroxy acids by transitional metal ions¹⁻⁷. But Tl(III) oxidation of alpha-hydroxy acids has not been attempted. This paper describes the kinetics of the oxidation of some alpha-hydroxyacids like mandelic (MA), atrolactic(ALA), benzoic (BA) and benzylphenyl glycollic acids (BPGA) by Tl(III) acetate in aqueous acetic acid.

Experimental

Thallium(III) acetate was prepared according to the method given by Henry⁸. Mandelic acid (m.p. 119°) and benzoic acid (m.p. 150°) were of Fluka variety. Atrolactic acid (m.p. 117°) and benzylphenyl glycollic acids were prepared from acetophenone⁹ and chalcone epoxide¹⁰ respectively. Glacial acetic acid used as the solvent was of S. Merck G. R. variety. Redistilled water was used for preparing different compositions of solvent mixture. All other chemicals used were of either AnalaR or reagent grade.

Kinetic experiments were initiated by mixing equal volumes of two solutions (pre-equilibrated at the reaction temperature), one containing Tl(III) acetate and the other alpha-hydroxy acid in a fixed composition of acetic acid-water mixture (v/v). The experiments were conducted at constant ionic strength and acidity. The kinetics of the reactions were followed by estimating unreacted Tl(III) at various time intervals by an iodometric procedure⁹ against standard thiosulphate, using starch as indicator.

Stoichiometry and Product analysis : Stoichiometric studies between alpha-hydroxy acids and Tl(III) acetate indicate 1 : 1 mole ratio. The product from benzoic acid was benzophenone which was isolated and characterised by its 2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazone derivative (m.p. 239°) and from its I.R. spectra. The product analysis from mandelic acid oxidation showed a mixture of benzaldehyde and benzoic acid. Since benzaldehyde is very much susceptible to aerial oxidation, the presence of benzoic acid was observed in the oxidation of mandelic acid.

The over all reaction for alpha-hydroxy acid oxidation to a carbonyl compound may be represented by the following empirical equation :

Results and Discussion

Tl(III) oxidation of benzoic acid has been studied in detail and the results of kinetic experiments in 90% (v/v) acetic acid-water mixture at an acidity of 1.071 M HClO_4 are presented in Table 1. The ionic strength has been maintained constant by addition of sodium perchlorate. The reactions were carried out under pseudo-unimolecular conditions taking organic acid always in excess. The reactions exhibit a total second order, first order each with respect to Tl(III) and

TABLE 1—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON [Tl(III)] AND [BA]
SOLVENT = 90%HOAc (v/v).

$[\text{HClO}_4] = 1.071M, \mu = 1.124M, \text{Temperature } 30^\circ.$

[Tl(III)] × 10 ³ M	[BA] × 10 M	k × 10 ⁵ sec ⁻¹
6.230	4.40	36.62
6.230	4.00	33.20
6.230	3.40	28.30
6.230	3.00	25.10
6.230	2.40	20.15
6.230	2.00	15.83
6.43	2.00	13.80
6.853	2.00	11.63
7.083	2.00	9.21
8.313	2.00	6.91
8.543	2.00	4.37
8.763	2.00	3.68

TABLE 2—RATE DATA FOR HYDROXY ACIDS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES.

$$[\text{Tl(III)}] \times 10^3 = 6.23M, [\text{Acid}] = 2 \times 10^{-1}M, [\text{HClO}_4] = 1.071M, \mu = 1.124M$$

Acid	$k \times 10^5$ in sec^{-1}				E in KCal/mole	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ in e. u. at 30° .	ΔF^\ddagger Kcal/mole at 30° .
	30°	35°	40°	45°			
MA	9.52	12.62	15.73	20.52	10.6	44.0	23.3
ALA	12.63	17.82	27.83	37.51	12.9	35.7	23.7
BA	15.83	22.71	32.13	40.32	13.4	33.8	23.0
BPGA	20.64	34.75	53.71	93.45	16.7	9.9	19.1

hydroxy acid concentrations. Any particular run has been found to give a linear plot for about 75% of the reaction. The duplicate rate measurements were reproducible to $\pm 3\%$. Second order rate constant at 30° has been calculated from the slope of the linear plot of k_{obs} vs. [BA] to be $0.830 \times 10^{-5} M^{-1} \text{sec}^{-1}$. The pseudo unimolecular rate constants for all the hydroxy acids under identical conditions have been recorded in Table 2 along with Arrhenius parameters. The empirical rate law conforming to the second order kinetics of the reaction may be written as :

$$-\frac{d \text{Tl(III)}}{dt} = k[\text{Tl(III)}] [\alpha\text{-hydroxy acid}].$$

The first order rate constants for the disappearance of Tl(III) at any [BA], acidity and ionic strength, have been observed to decrease with increasing [Tl(III)] (Table 1). This uncommon observation has also been made in the Tl(III) oxidation^{1,2} of aromatic ketones and alpha-phenyl ethyl alcohol.

Acid Dependence : The reaction is acid catalysed and exhibits a first order dependence on perchloric acid concentration. The results for benzilic acid oxidation are incorporated in Table 3. A similar rate dependence on acid has also been observed in the case of ketone oxidation by Tl(III).

TABLE 3—ACID DEPENDENCE ON REACTION RATE

$$[\text{Tl(III)}] \times 10^3 = 6.23M, [\text{BA}] = 2 \times 10^{-1}M, \text{Solvent} = 90\% \text{HOAc (v/v)}, \text{Temperature } 30^\circ.$$

[HClO ₄]	$k_1 \times 10^5 \text{ Sec}^{-1}$	$\frac{k \times 10^5}{[\text{HClO}_4]}$ in $M^{-1} \text{sec}^{-1}$
0.953	20.13	0.210
1.071	21.92	0.204
1.607	32.28	0.208
1.875	37.20	0.205
2.142	42.88	0.204
2.450	50.23	0.208

The acid catalysis can be explained by the acid-base interaction with Tl(III) acetate to produce more active Tl(III) species according to the following scheme :

$\text{Tl}^+(\text{OAc})_2$ is known to be the active species for oxidation in aqueous acetic acid mixtures containing perchloric acid^{3,1,2}.

Solvent Influence : In order to establish the nature of Tl(III) species participating in the reaction, the rate of oxidation has been studied in acetic acid-water mixtures of varying concentrations. The rate of the reaction has been found to increase with increasing acetic acid content in the solvent mixture and the data for the oxidation of benzilic acid are recorded in Table 4.

TABLE 4—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON SOLVENT COMPOSITION

$$[\text{Tl(III)}] \times 10^3 = 6.23M, [\text{BA}] = 2 \times 10^{-1}M, [\text{HClO}_4] = 1.071M, \mu = 1.24M, \text{Temperature } 30^\circ$$

% of HOAc (v/v)	$k \times 10^5 \text{ sec}^{-1}$
90	15.83
85	14.45
80	13.10
75	12.00
70	10.50

The plot of $\log k$ vs. the reciprocal of dielectric constant has been observed to be linear with a positive slope indicating a positive ion-dipole reaction^{1,5}. The value of 'r', the minimum distance of approach between the ion and the dipole has been calculated from the slope of the above plot to be 1.09 \AA , considering a monopositive thallium species as the active oxidant. This value is of reasonable magnitude.

Effect of added salt : Addition of either sodium sulphate or sodium perchlorate seems to have negligible effect on the rate of oxidation. However, the rate of the reaction has been found to decrease considerably (Table 5) by addition of sodium chloride or sodium acetate. This large decrease in rate by addition of chloride and acetate ions can be attributed to the formation of species like $\text{Tl}(\overset{\ominus}{\text{OAc}})_4$, $\text{Tl}(\text{OAc})_2 \text{Cl}^\ominus$ or TlCl_2 .

TABLE 5—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON ADDED SALT

[Tl(III)] = $6.23 \times 10^{-3} M$, [BA] = $2 \times 10^{-1} M$, [HClO₄] = 1.071 M
Solvent = 90% HOAc-H₂O(v/v), Temperature 30°.

Salt	[Salt] × 10 ² M	k × 10 ⁵ sec ⁻¹
Nil	—	15.83
NaClO ₄	2.00	15.72
Na ₂ SO ₄	2.00	15.13
NaCl	0.20	6.49
NaOAc	2.00	6.34

Nature of Tl(III) species : Since the oxidation has been carried out in aqueous acetic acid containing perchloric acid, the following species of Tl(III) are expected to be involved in the oxidation : Tl(OAc)₃, Tl(OAc)₂ClO₄, Tl(OAc)₂⁺, Tl(OAc)₂⁻, Tl⁺(OAc)₂OAc⁻ and Tl₂²⁺(OAc)₄. The ion pair Tl⁺(OAc)₂OAc⁻ and the double salt Tl₂(OAc)₄ have been shown to play insignificant role in the redox reactions in acetic acid medium^{1,7}. The observed rate reduction in presence of acetate ion is due to the formation of less reactive Tl(OAc)₂⁻. Therefore, Tl(OAc)₂⁺ may not be considered as an effective oxidising species. Although Tl(OAc)₃ and Tl(OAc)₂ClO₄ have been suggested^{1,2,17} to be the active species in the redox reactions, the rate dependence on dielectric constant of the medium and on the concentration of perchloric acid suggests a positive thallic ion species as an active oxidant in the present study. Proton is known to abstract an acetate group from the coordination sphere of the thallic ion and therefore the following equilibria are considered to be responsible for giving the thallic ion species of higher reactivity.

These equilibria are more favourable in aqueous acetic acid and therefore, Tl(OAc)₂⁺ seems to be the active electrophilic species in the present oxidation of alpha-hydroxy acids by Tl(III) in aqueous acetic acid media. A similar conclusion has also been drawn by us in the Tl(III) oxidation of ketones in aqueous acetic acid medium. Tl(OAc)₂⁺ has also been shown to be the important reactive species in the oxidation of olefins⁸.

Structure-Reactivity Relation : The reactivity of the different alpha-hydroxy acids conforms to the following order :

This order of reactivity has also been observed in the oxidation of alpha-hydroxy acids by Pb(IV) which is iso-electronic with Tl(III). The order of reactivity indicates that the bulk of the group controls the rate of oxidation. The rate data do not correlate well with either E_s or σ^{*} values^{1,8}. This suggests simultaneous operation of both polar and steric effects in the reaction. Entropy of activation values have been found to have large negative values indicating rigid transition states.

Mechanism : Tl(III) unlike other metal ion oxidants, essentially behaves as a two electron oxidant^{1,6,19-20}.

Oxidation of alpha-hydroxy acids of the type

by two electron oxidants like Cr(VI) involves a rate determining C-H bond cleavage. Although this mechanism may not operate in benzoic acid as it does not contain any direct C-H bond, a similar mechanism probably operates. Hydroxy acids are known to form chelated species with many metals²¹. Pb(IV) acetate which is iso-electronic with Tl(III) acetate shows similar behaviour as an oxidant, and has been shown to oxidise alpha-hydroxy acids and 1,2-glycols through the formation of chelated species²². Tl(III) is also known to form co-ordinate with compounds containing oxygen²³.

In view of the above considerations, the oxidation of alpha-hydroxy acids by Tl(III) in aqueous acetic acid media may be suggested to proceed via the formation of a chelated complex which subsequently decomposes by an oxidative decarboxylation to the corresponding carbonyl compound according to the following scheme :

This mechanism appears to be compatible for the alpha-hydroxy acids of both the types viz : HO-CH(COOH) and HO-CR(COOH). The increased

rate of oxidation with the successive replacement of the hydrogen by a methyl, phenyl or benzyl group may be traced to the steric influence of these groups in the formation of the transition state.

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